

Child Abuse and Security Challenges in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the link between child abuse and security challenges in Nigeria. General strain theory and social bond theory were adopted as the theoretical frame of the study. While the former explains how blocked opportunities among the lower class youths lead to delinquency, and consequently, to insecurity in the society, the latter explains how weakened bond to conventional social institutions reduces social control of young persons, and subsequently, leading to insecurity in the society. Thus, abuse of children will have a long-term effect and elicit deprivation that can later be expressed through delinquency or crime. The article principally relied on secondary data. The article concludes that child abuse has many social and psychological consequences and they are associated to security challenges in Nigeria. As differently indicated by the data cited in this article, most of the city hooligans, members of urban gangs, *Boko Haram* and other forms of criminal gangs are largely from lower classes and majority have in one way or the other experienced child abuse and neglect. To overcome the menace of child abuse in Nigeria and by implication the insecurity, the article recommended that the Government, NGOs, community members and families should provide means for child protection, poverty reduction, and creation of awareness, etc.

KEYWORDS: *child, child abuse, crime, security, security challenges*

INTRODUCTION

The problem of child abuse is not new to modern societies. This is because transition of society to (post) industrialism leads to new trends. Industrial Revolution for instance witnessed unprecedented economic and social transformations. This revolution was accompanied with rapid urbanization and industrialism, leading to a fundamentally new direction as it set the pace for modern capitalism (Lee & Newby, 2005). Although it brought many economic developments, the revolution was also inimical to the modern societies because it was accompanied with many social problems, including child abuse. Kendall (2011) assessed the negative effects of Industrial Revolution on families and children by citing an example of how families living in the cities had to buy food with their wages as they could no longer grow their own crops to consume or to barter for other resources. In addition, the suffering of the lower class families is invariably greater hardships for the children due to neglect, lack of education, hazardous labour and abuse. This scenario is presumably a harbinger for insecurity, as these children have not been, trained to become productive members of their future societies.

Consequently, the modern societies are increasingly becoming anomic, characterized by delinquency, deviance and crime in all nooks and crannies of the state. Drug abuse among children, youth (both men and women), prostitution, suicide, genocide, insurgency in North-East and terrorism in South-South, farmers/cattle herders conflict in North-West and Middle-Belt, ethnoreligious conflict, widespread and

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persistency of kidnapping, rape and ritual killings among others. The high rate of delinquency, deviance and crime in Nigeria can be linked to child abuse and neglect that continue to affect the proper upbringing and socialization of young persons in contemporary Nigeria; thereby decreasing the likelihood of achieving a relatively safe and secured society. In other words, child abuse is a remote or immediate predisposing factor for the rising security challenges in Nigeria. This is obvious given the fact that child abuse affects the psychological development of the children through, aggression, restiveness and disrespect for law and order. This article examines the link between child abuse and security challenges in Nigeria, forms of child abuse, causes of child abuse, as well, as how child abuse and neglect can affect security in Nigeria.

Conceptual Explanation

Child

The concept of *Child* can be understood historically or legally. From the historical point of view, child is an evolving term that in the past was seen as a miniature adult, but overtime meant a particular phase of life characterized by weakness and dependence on the older members of the society (Scott & Codd 2010). Historically, the emergence of childhood as a concept is traceable to the 17th Century. Before that period, not only in Africa, but in most of Europe, children were treated as miniature adults. That is why the topic of "apprenticeship" whereby child follows father or guardian to farm, workplace to be trained as future potential

future farmer, blacksmith, or butcher. For Scott & Codd (2010), the current understanding of the concept dates back to as recently as nineteenth century.

According to Rios-Kohn (2007), legal interpretation of 'child' today comes to delineate specific social roles appropriate to young people. In common, for instance, a child is one who had not attained the age of fourteen (14) years. Following United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), UNICEF (2014:1) defined a child "as a person below the age of 18, unless the laws of a particular country set the legal age for adulthood younger". The Committee on the Rights of the Child is the monitoring body for the Convention and has encouraged concerned States to review the age of majority if it is set below 18 and to increase the level of protection for all children under 18. Now, many global and local facts are made available to represent the picture of what childhood is in relation to economic and social policy, however they do not present a uniform picture (Brown, 2005). Hence, definition of child is not always uniform between two or more societies. What is regarded as child in Nigeria may be different from that of the United States or Malaysia. Yet, age bracket is very important in defining child in the modern societies irrespective of geographical differences.

Child Abuse

The phenomenon of child abuse is a global melancholy that continues to endanger the safety and security of many innocent children worldwide. According to Abdullahi (2000) Child abuse is a broad term for different types of child misuse and neglect. According to Edu and Edu (as cited in Dada, 2013) child abuse connotes willful maltreatment of a child, including; acts of commission (abuse) and omission (neglect). Therefore, child abuse has to do with the harmful treatment of a child. In other words, child abuse entails a wide range of situations, which Kadushin (1980) identified as follows: -

1. Physical abuse
2. Emotional or mental harm
3. Malnourishment, poor clothing and shelter
4. Denial of adequate medical care and treatment
5. Denial of education or failure to send to school regularly
6. Exploitation and overwork
7. Exposure to criminogenic or demoralizing circumstances

From the above, it could also be said that child abuse entails the physical, economic, emotional, health, and sexual abuse of children. Indeed, the most widespread form of abuse is neglect, namely, a parent or guardian's inability to provide a child with enough food, adequate clothing, shelter, medical care, and education (Abdullahi, 2000). In other words, child neglect connotes a situation in which a minor is denied his natural and cultural right to basic necessities of life.

Security

The concept of security is a complex and encircling term that encompasses several dimensions. Security means different things to different people, as it may be viewed from different angles. Security however, can be described as stability and continuity of livelihood (stable and steady income), predictability of routine life (knowing what to expect), protection from crime (feeling safe), and freedom from psychological harm (safety from emotional stress which results from the assurance or knowing that one is wanted, accepted, loved and protected in one's community or

neighbourhood and by people around (Ighomereho and Akpor-Robaro, 2013). Abdullahi (2009) defined security from a 'crime prevention' point of view, when he defined security as prevention from all criminal and aberrant activities.

Security may be seen from an objective or subjective sense. Objective security entails freedom from threat and danger, while subjective security entails feeling of safety and protection, including absence of fear and/or psychological harm. Security may also be seen as positive or negative. Negative security refers to condition in which individuals or parties have the freedom to identify risks and threats to their wellbeing and values, while positive security refers to a condition in which individuals or parties have the freedom to communicate the identified risks and threats to other individuals or parties, with a view to control or reduce its impact (Gjorv, 2012). One may also look at political, human, economic, environmental, cultural, domestic or strategic security etc. Thus, it all depends on the place, time and context at which security is mentioned or discussed. In this article, security is viewed as a condition that is characterize with relatively low level of criminal activities.

Types of Child Abuse

1. **Physical Abuse:-** This includes physical attempt to attack, intimidate, threaten, discipline or harm a child. It involves hitting a child with cane or any other object, pushing, punching, slapping, and kicking among others.
2. **Economic Abuse:-** This connotes the practice of paying a child less than the actual or agreed price of his labour, or less than the standard minimum wage. For example, most children that engage in child labour are economically abused. Abdullahi (2000) maintained that they is no guarantee that the female child labourer will be, paid her entitlement at the end of the contract period.
3. **Sexual Abuse:-** This entails using sexual activity verbally or physically to harm a child. For example, rape with or without consent, use of hands, other body parts to, intentionally touch child's genitals, exposing children to sexual signs, symbols and/or wordings.
4. **Emotional Abuse:-** This has to do with the act of inflicting psychological harm or disturbing the mood and emotional state of a child. Physical, sexual and economic abuse of children may lead to their emotional abuse.
5. **Cyber Abuse:-** This involves the use of networked computers or internet technology to emotionally or sexually harm a child. For example, online sexual solicitation, child pornography, paedophile attacks etc.

Of all the five types of child abuse mentioned above, the first four (child physical abuse, child economic abuse, child sexual abuse, and child emotional abuse) are more common in Nigeria.

Causes of Child Abuse

Yahaya (1990) identified macroeconomic factors such as unemployment, inflation, low level of income coupled with other governments policies and programmes like rural neglect, structural adjustment (SAP), budgetary and expenditure priorities have succeeded in creating hostile economic atmosphere for child development. Abdullahi (2000) maintained that poverty has pushed many male

children into child begging, and many female children into child hawking. Whereas the male children are sent to urban cities in pursuit of *Quranic* knowledge (*almajirci*), the female children are sent to hawk, so as to, help accumulate money that could be used for her marital expenses.

Ebigbo (as cited in Nte et al., 2009) argued that the main factors that push children into the streets include marital problems or instability in the home, poverty, hunger, insecurity, broken families, unemployment, illiteracy, housing difficulties among others. Calheiros (2013) believed that poverty, family structure, parent's educational level and parent's childhood experience of child abuse are causal factors of child abuse. Conversely, some parents lack awareness that some cultural practices violates the rights of children like beating children (a form of discipline in African societies) (Olusegun and Idowu, 2016).

Bicakci, Er and Aral (2016) differentiated between socioeconomic factors, characteristics of the abuser and the characteristics of the abused child. To them, the causes of child abused include socioeconomic factors like; low income families and unemployed guardian, Characteristics of the abuser like; young age, childhood experience of abuse and low level education, and the characteristics of the abused childlike; children with mental or physical disabilities, hyperactivity disorder or chronic disease. Thus, the causes of child abuse include illiteracy, socioeconomic factors like poverty and unemployment, social factors like pathological families and even the abused child features like physical or mental disabilities.

Incidences of Child Abuse in Nigeria

Child abuse is very common, especially in developing countries. In Nigeria, for instance, there are many instances in which children are either, abused by guardians, community members or even parents. A survey, The 2014 Nigeria Violence against Children Study, carried out by the National Population Commission (NPOPC) in collaboration with the US Centers for Disease Control and the UNICEF (cited in Akor, 2015) revealed a high prevalence of sexual, physical and emotional violence against children in the country. Many lower class children, orphans and *Almajiris* are, abused in a broad daylight in the country. Daily Trust (2017) reported that the Chairman of the Supreme Court of Nigeria, Justice Ibrahim Tanko raised concern over rampant cases of child abuse nationwide.

Punch Nigeria (2018) reported that the Lagos State Domestic and Sexual Violence Response Team said that from January to August 2018, the team handled 245 cases of child abuse. Vanguard News (2019) reported that a 26 year old man was arrested over indecent assault on a 2 year old baby. A male parent was arrested in Calabar for attempting to sell his own 2 male children, for not more than 350 thousand naira (Vanguard News, 2019). Vanguard News (2019) also reported that a Magistrate Court in Lagos (Ikeja) remanded a 29 year old female teacher for sexually assaulting her 4 year old student.

Child Abuse and Security Challenges in Nigeria

According to Currie and Takin (2006) child abuse roughly doubles the likelihood that an individual engage in many types of crime. For Abdulhamid and Sunusi (2016) the increasing level of street children is not only affecting

national development, but also a huge threat to national security. Goment (2017) in his study on parental neglect and juvenile delinquency of *almajirai* in Kano State captured how young persons end up becoming delinquents and career criminals. He argued that when children are left unsupervised, they will rely mainly on the values of informal groups they associate with, which makes them inculcate values that are sometimes contrary to societal expectations. It is also important to consider that these young abandoned, abused and hopeless children are like normal individuals with goals, needs and aspirations. Feeling of hopelessness and social rejection may culminate into frustration. Consequently, these children may engage in delinquent acts like theft, and may later on, be part of urban gangs, political thugs and/or career criminals engaging in behaviours like kidnapping, rape, ritual killing, drug trafficking, insurgent attacks, ethnic and religious conflicts etc. Thus, continuously engaging in acts that are detrimental to the safety and security of the society.

A report on search for common ground by UNICEF in 2012 accounted for recruitment of children by violent criminal groups. The report provided that, recruitment of children by northern religious/ethnic groups like *Boko Haram* and ethnoreligious militias in Jos is targeted at *almajiris* (children often sent to streets to beg) which can make them more susceptible to recruitment. Cult groups (generally located in Southern Nigeria) also pull children merely voluntarily or under peer influence, targeting the most vulnerable particularly street children, those in need of livelihood and/or lacks adequate parental care. The report also suggest that gangs/thugs when recruiting children, generally target strong and intelligent children that lacked parental care, making them easy targets to be lured by promise of quick money and a source of livelihood.

According to Goment (2017) Nigeria Best Forum in 2013 reported an incidence involving a 19 year old *almajiri* who on 13th July, 2010 attempted to kill the Emir of Kano at the instance of a cleric, Malam Haladu (who according to the culprit is his spiritual adviser) was detected by a smart palace guard. The culprit equally admitted that he just came back from Abuja, where he robbed an Igbo man of 3million Naira at Jabi Garage. United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2019) reported that *Boko Haram* and ISWAP have recruited an estimate of about 8000 children since 2009. The report added that the figures may be underestimated because of difficulties associated with collecting a reliable data. According to Sahara Reporters (2017) UNICEF opined that *Boko Haram* have used 83 child suicide bombers in 2017, which is four times as many child suicide bombers used in all of 2016.

Theoretical Framework

This paper adopted General Strain Theory (GST) and Social Bond Theory in providing theoretical explanation of child abuse and security challenges in Nigeria. Robert S. Agnew in 1992 develop the GST to explain how micro level forces arousing from negative social relationships adduces strain on individuals which may subsequently leads to crime. For Lanier, Henry and Anastasia (2015) the two kinds of strain, structural and psychological strain are interrelated in Agnew's GST. Agnew (2009) defined strain as conditions and events, that are not liked by individuals. According to the theory, criminality is a consequence of 'negative affective

state', which include anger, frustration and other negative emotions that emerge as a result of negative and destructive social relationships.

Agnew (2009) argued that strain is aroused when individuals lose something good, receive something bad or cannot get what they want. Precisely, the sources of strain include:

1. Strain emanating from failure to achieve positively cherished goals (i.e people that aspire for wealth but lacked financial or educational resources)
2. Strain emanating from failure to meet expectation or discrepancy between expectation and reality (feeling of relative deprivation)
3. Strain emanating from presentation of negatively cherished stimuli (i.e child abuse, criminal victimization, peer conflict)
4. Strain emanating from removal of positively valued stimuli (i.e divorce, break up, death of loved ones)

Agnew's explanation of strain revolves around how sources of strain could put pressure on an individual and culminate into negative affective states (frustration, anger, disappointed, depression) which could consequently induce criminal behaviour. Siegel (2012) argued that the greater the frequency and intensity of strain experienced, the greater their impact on the affected individuals and the more likely they are to cause criminality.

Accordingly, the theory explained how strain is imposed on children through presentation of negatively valued stimuli. Children that are abused and neglected are pushed to an emotionally charged state of anger, depression, frustration, disappointment that could trigger their engagement in anti-social behaviours. Abused and neglected children can easily be lured into joining criminal groups like cult groups, urban gangs, terrorist groups like *Boko Haram* and Niger Delta militants to vent their anger and frustration on the society, consequently compounding the security challenges facing Nigeria.

Agnew's General Strain Theory is presently the dominant form of strain in criminology (Agnew, 2009). The theory was able to successfully interconnect sociological and psychological factors to explain strain and predict delinquent/criminal. Agnew's work illuminates the concept of strain and direct future research plans (Siegel, 2012). However, the theory was criticised for arguing that strain indirectly affects delinquency/criminality through negative emotionality and low self-constraint (Davidowitz, 2017). Conversely, Davidowitz believed that high levels of negative emotionality and low self-constraint are the mediating factors that are most important for predicting delinquent/criminal behaviour. The theory ambitiously seeks to elaborate strain and provide multiple factors that could push criminal behaviour, while neglecting the pull factors. In essence, some individuals facing strain may not engage in crime until when they are influenced by their friends or associates.

While strain theory explained why individuals choose to commit crime, social bond theory explained why individuals conform to societal norms and state laws. The theory was developed by Travis Hirschi (1969) as a critique for social learning theories. For social bond theory, rather than to

explain why individuals engage in crime, it is more important to understand why individuals conform. The theory argued that individuals conform to societal rules because of social control, which is determined by individual's bond to conventional social institutions. In other words, what restrains individuals from committing crime is their bond to conventional parents, friends, school authorities or teachers, coaches, employers, career ambition and so on.

Hirschi believed that social bond has four elements, whose interrelationship controls subsequent behaviour (Siegel, 2012). These four elements include: attachment, commitment, involvement and belief. *Attachment* connotes emotional affinity that an individual has for conventional others (i.e parents, siblings,) which makes him/her respect their views, expectations and not willing to engage in acts that may affect their relationship or disappoint them. *Commitment* refers to individuals investment of time and energy in conventional responsibilities like getting education or entrepreneurship development. Such individuals are less likely to engage in activities (like crime) that will be detrimental to their success or personal goals. For *involvement*, Hirschi observed that individuals that are involved in conventional activities has little time for crime commission. For example, a young person who is involved in school and recreational activities as well as family responsibilities is less likely to have time to, even think of committing crime. Finally, Hirschi pointed at individual's *belief* system. He was concerned with the ability and authority of moral norms to sanction individual's behaviors and actions. Individuals with strong belief in moral norms of the society are likely to desist from illegal acts.

Hirschi (1969) argued that individuals feel free to commit crime because of weak social bond to conventional social institutions like family, peer group, school and religion. Precisely, lack of emotional affinity or attachment to family members and other significant others may weaken an individual's social control, which influences his/her choice to commit crime. Hence, most of the abused and neglected children have weak attachment with their parents and other family members, which reduces their social control and increases their probability of committing crime and/or engaging in antisocial behaviors. In the case of some abused children like *almajiri*, they do not only have poor attachment but also have weakened commitment to conventional social institutions. These abused children lack parental control or supervision and access to formal education that reduces their level of social control and makes them more likely to commit crime. Thus, lack of control due to weakened bond to some conventional social institutions push some abused children to engage in criminal and terrorist activities that are detrimental to the security of Nigeria.

While Hirschi's social bond theory remains highly celebrated and influential in criminological discourse, as it is among the most empirically tested theories, the theory is not without some criticisms. Siegel (2012) observed that not all the elements of the theory are equally important, because, research evidence suggests that there may be difference. Some adolescents who report high levels of "involvement" (which should according to, the theory reduce delinquency) are involved in criminal behaviour. The theory is also difficult in explaining white collar or corporate crimes.

Conclusion

Child abuse has many social and psychological consequences, and security challenges are, also associated with it in Nigeria. Because most of the city hooligans, and members of urban gangs, *Boko Haram* members and other forms of criminal gangs are largely from lower classes and they in one way or the other experienced child abuse and neglect through *almajiri* system or lack of education at all. Since the role of child abuse in the proliferation of crime and insecurity cannot be, overemphasized, it is high time for Nigerians to realise the impact of child abuse in the destabilization of national security. In other words, the security of any nation is dependent upon how well children are treated, socialized and groomed. It is, often said that, 'children are the leaders of tomorrow', if so, then it remains paramount to ask which type of leaders do we wish to breed? And what type of future are we creating for ourselves and future generations to come?

Recommendations

To overcome the menace of child abuse in Nigeria and by implication insecurity, the article recommended the following:

1. The Government should enact child protection laws that can guarantee the freedom of children from child abuse from the hands of guardians and even parents.
2. The Government has to develop policies that can address poverty in Nigeria, because majority of children being, abused are from poor family backgrounds.
3. The fact that *almajiri* system is characterised by untold child abuse, the entire system has, be transformed and formalised so that Government has a stake in the affairs of the schools. This will include Government's intervention through food and accommodation, training for the teachers and emolument for the teachers.
4. NGOs can also help in fighting child abuse in Nigeria through creation of awareness on the consequences of child abuse on the child development and on security in the country.
5. Community members can also help in fighting child abuse through collective efforts at helping orphans and reporting signs of child abuse in the neighbourhood.
6. Families should also have a stake on the good treatment of their children. They can help in fighting child abuse through warmth for the younger ones and ensuring that they are properly catered for, so, that the children will not be seeking for assisting from neighbouring houses or members of the society, which is a recipe for child abuse by outsiders.

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